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Improving 4-C skills for senior secondary vocational school graduates

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Abstract

Senior Secondary Vocational School (SSVS) is designed to prepare graduates to become middle-level workers. This study aims to find learning models that are effective in increasing critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration, which are very important in the era of Industry 4.0.

Critical thinking and creativity are two complementary thinking skills especially for solving complex problems. To develop the skills students have to practice solving problems familiar with everyday life. Communication and collaboration skills are two very important abilities in social life. To develop these skills, students should practice group work in a social interaction. Thus collaborative project based learning (CPjBL) is considered to be an appropriate instructional model to develop four skills simultaneously.

This study applied the 4-D model, then the learning model was empirically tested through control group pretest posttest design. t test and effect size test was used to check the effectiveness of the instructional model. The analysis result showed that CPjBL was effective in developing critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration skills for SSVS students.

Keywords

critical thinking; creativity; communication; collaboration; collaborative project based learning

1 Introduction

In Indonesia, Senior Secondary Vocational School (SSVS/SMK) is designed to prepare graduates to become middle-level workers in certain fields (Law No. 20/2003: Article 15-explanation). However, data shows that SSVE graduates are the biggest contributors to unemployment (Tempo.Co: Nov 15, 2017; Jawa Pos: Nov 17, 2017). Often SSVS graduates fail to compete in the selection to enter the workforce (Samani. Cholikh, Buditjahjana, 2016). Similarly, the study of Newhouse and Suryadarma (2009) conclude that public appreciation of

SSVS is not high. Therefore the Government of Indonesia issue Presidential Instruction No. 9/2016 on SSVS revitalization.

Industrial era 4.0 has recently entered into many countries, including Indonesia. The World Economic Forum (WEF) (2016) study reports that industry 4.0 has brought a change of work patterns which is driven by mobile internet and cloud technology, power and big data processing, new energy supplies and technologies, and the internet of things. The four core-work related skills that are needed now are complex problem skills, social skills, process skills, system skills (WEF, 2016: 22). Similar to those findings, the Economist-Intelligence Unit study (2015: 8) found five skills needed in the future, they are problem solving, team working, communication, critical thinking and creativity.

When examined more deeply, the skills found by WEF and The Economist will lead to 4 core skills namely critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration (4-C) which are called the learning and innovation skills by Trilling and Fadel (2009: 49-60) and super skills by Kivunja (2015: 224), because they are the most important skills in the 21st century. This study aims to find a learning model that is able to develop critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration skills for SSVS students, so that they are able to join the employment field in industrial era 4.0.

2 Theoretical Framework

1.1. Critical Thinking and Creativity

Critical thinking and creativity are two complementary thinking skills for solving complex problems (Paul and Elder, 2008). Associated with Bloom taxonomy, critical thinking includes two levels of thinking, namely analyze and evaluation, while creativity is a level above them (Wilson, 2016). While Marrapodi (2003) mentions critical thinking is the stage of evaluating an information or idea, while creativity is the stage of its expansion. Thus, although complementary critical thinking and creativity are two separate capabilities.

Ruggiero (in Murawski, 2014: 25) says critical thinking is the art of thinking about thinking, so that it seems to be the peak of thinking ability. People who think critically do not directly accept someone's opinion but will look for other information as a comparison (Karakoc, 2016: 28; Murawski, 2014: 26). Thus, people who think critically apply deductive and inductive thinking simultaneously. Critical thinking is a high order thinking skills that have six aspects, namely interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, explanation and self regulation (Facione, 2013: 5; Koeswiyah, 2012).

How to develop critical thinking? Snyder and Snyder (2008: 93-94) mention that to foster critical thinking skills, learning must involve students actively, focus more on processes and not results, and apply challenging evaluation patterns. Similarly, Murawski (2014: 27) mentions challenging tasks or questions will encourage students to develop their critical thinking. To help students more easily develop critical thinking skills, tasks or questions must be related to their daily lives (Samani and Palupi, 2013).

Creativity can take the form of process (creative thinking) and results (creative products) (Cropley, 2011). Creative products are produced by creative thinking but creative thinking does not necessarily produce creative products. Meanwhile, Runco and Jaeger (2012: 92) states that creativity requires two aspects, namely originality and effectiveness. In line with that, Amabile (in Gino and Ariely, 2012: 445) defines creativity as the ability to produce new ideas that are useful for the needs. Original but ineffective means unuseful ideas, on the contrary effective or useful but not original ideas does not mean something new.

Associated with work, creativity is the first step towards innovation (Baer, 2012: 1102). Creativity refers to ideas, while innovation designates the implementation of these ideas in solving a problem. The Santa Fe Institute Working Group (2015: 17) states that creativity is

influenced by abilities in memory, divergent thinking, convergent thinking, and flow. While Filsaime in Nurlaela and Ismayati (2015: 24), and Liu and Schoenwetter (2004: 802) states that creativity has four aspects of fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration.

Through a series of studies, Boyd and Goldenberg (2013) proved that creativity can be developed through systematic inventive thinking (SIT), while Tan, Lee, Ponnisamy, Koh and Tan (2016) mention creativity can grow well if learning provides opportunities for students to apply their ideas. Thus providing opportunities for trial and error is the key in fostering the ability to think creatively. In the context of automotive technicians, trouble shooting training is an effective way to foster students' critical thinking skills and creativity.

1.2. Communication and Collaboration

Communication and collaboration skills are two very important abilities in social life. Both are complementary in social interaction (Nazaro & Stazzabosco, 2009). Research conducted by The Economist Intelligence Unit (2015: 3) concludes that both are also very useful in future work. For automotive technicians, the type of communication that is needed is interpersonal communication that has five aspects, namely emotional intelligence, body language, posture, sensitivity to the audience through appropriate behavior, and active listening (Koehler and Wesson, 2014: 2). In line with that, Hutagalung (2017: 3) mentions five aspects namely clear voice, good grammar, nice expression, viewing others, easy to understand. Meanwhile, Kapur (2013) mentions obstacles that often occur in communication, namely environmental and physical barriers, semantic barriers, cultural barriers, psychological barriers, perception of reality.

Collaboration is mutual engagement between two or more people to achieve agreed goals (Lai, 2011: 2). Unlike cooperation that emphasizes the division of labor, collaboration is more flexible (Child and Shaw, 2018: 18). Katzenbach and Smith (in Reeves, Xyrichis and Zwarenstein, 2018: 1) mention collaboration can take the form of working groups, pseudo teams, potential teams, real teams, and high performance teams. The difference between the five depends on the solidity of the team concerned. In the context of automotive technicians the collaboration pattern tends to be loose because the work is simple, so it can be categorized as a working group, which according to McMaster University (2016) has five aspects: sharing information and experiences, responsibility and accountability, cooperation, support for innovation, and mutual trust and respect.

In collaboration the quality of communication is one of the determining factors (Hidayanto and Setyadi, 2014: 96). Job mistakes often occur due to misunderstandings in communication between members of the work team. In interpersonal communication, miscommunication is often caused by cultural factors. What the speaker means is understood differently by the listener (Koehler and Wesson, 2014), therefore mutual understanding of culture between members of working groups is very necessary (Schadewitz, 2009: 37). Besides that, the obstacles that occur in collaboration are lack of collaborative skills, free-riding, competence status, and friendship (Le, Janssen and Wubbels, 2018: 109-110).

The similarity of goals and understanding of the work handled also greatly influences the effectiveness of collaboration (Reeves, Xyrichis and Zwarenstein, 2018: 2), so that brief discussions before starting work are very important in the working group (Samani, Suparji, Rahmadian, 2017: 200). In trouble shooting on the automotive field, idea differences for resolving damage often occur, so members of the working group must convey each other's ideas to avoid mistakes in work steps. The culture of collaboration is more easily developed through team of culture, community culture, and network culture (Callahan, Schenk and White, 2008: 7).

Collaboration and communication, especially interpersonal communication is very important in the world of work, but unfortunately it is rarely taught in schools (Callahan,

Schenk and White, 2008: 1), because schools more emphasize on the individual abilities of student. In contrast, in the technological era almost all jobs are carried out in groups (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2007). As a result, many SSVS graduates fail in job selection not because they are less skilled, but because they do not have the ability to communicate and collaborate (Samani, 2014).

Communication and collaboration are not sufficiently theorized but must be in the form of daily behavior, so the development of these two abilities must be carried out through practical work training (Hole, 2015: 1973-1974). In other words students learn in work groups so that productive social interactions occur. Therefore collaborative project based learning (CPjBL) is considered to be an appropriate instructional model to develop those skills simultaneously.

1.3. Collaborative Project Based Learning

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a student-driven, teacher-facilitated approach to learning (Bell, 2010: 39). In Collaborative Project Based Learning (CPjBL) students work in groups that are tailored to the competencies that students must master and are associated with the context of their lives (Chen, Hernandez, Dong, 2015: 28). Meanwhile Donnelly and Fitzmaurice (2003) mention that CPjBL applies a multidisciplinary project approach that is tailored to the student environment with more emphasis on student activities. The five main characteristics of CPjBL are learning by doing, real world problems, interdisciplinary, collaborative group work, the role of tutors as a “guide on the side”, and end product oriented (Harmer and Stokes, 2014: 4-6).

Implementation of the CPjBL requires adequate preparation, for both students and teachers. In the learning process, students construct new knowledge based on prior knowledge. Because the CPjBL applies the principle of learning by doing and the teacher/instructor acts as a mentor from the side, students must have sufficient knowledge about the project carried out and have sufficient experience in collaboration (Bell, 2014: 42). Teachers must also understand how to implement the principle of "to guide from the side" and how to evaluate the competencies achieved by each student. Designing projects that fit the competencies students have to achieve and corresponds to their environment and how to apply the above five principles is a challenge for teachers (Jamal, Essawi1 & Tilchin, 2014)

CPjBL has been proven to be successfully applied in universities (Donnelly and Fitzmaurice, 2003; Zhang, Peng and Hung, 2009; Chen, Hernandez, Dong, 2015). Students at the universities certainly have maturity in thinking and behaving, so the principle of learning by doing and learning independently can work well. However, there has not been many researches on the application of CPjBL at the high school level, especially in vocational schools and associated with the development of 4-C skills.

In this study, the project undertaken by students is trouble shooting a motorcycle brake system which is one of the competencies that must be mastered by SSVS students. CPjBL application on the topic of trouble shooting will encourage students to think critically to find problems occurred, think creatively to find solutions, communicate and collaborate because the project is done in groups. This ability will be integratively built when students work and students will be motivated to work because they have the freedom to do what they think (Halmer and Stokes, 2014: 15).

3 Methods

This study applied the 4-D model (define, design, develop and disseminate) (Thiagarajan, Semmel and Semmel, 1994), but only to the stage of development. The learning model was empirically tested through control group pre-test post test design (Krathwohl: 1998: 510-511).

The study was conducted at Department of Automotive Technology “SMK-X” on even semester, academic year 2017/2018. Topics used was brake system that includes both theory and practice activities and has medium-level of difficulty. The experimental group applied CPjBL while the control group applied a learning model that had been used so far, namely direct instruction followed by assignments.

To measure critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration skills observation sheets used. Expert judgment by 3 experts was applied to check the content validity and construct validity of the instrument. Reliability of the instrument was tested by inter rater (Borich, 1994), with results 97.96% for critical thinking, 93.76% for creativity, 92.07% for communication and 92.06% for collaboration skills. Thus, the four observation sheets are reliable.

To ensure the equality between the experimental group and the control group, a pretest was carried out and the results were tested by t test. After the learning process completed, post test was carried out and the results were tested by t test, followed by the effect size test (Cohen's d) which was done using a scientific calculator.

4 Findings

Table 1 shows the pre-test and post-test scores, both for experimental and control group. *t* test analysis against the pre-test score between the two groups shows the result: *p* for critical thinking = 0.63, *p* for creativity = 0.65, *p* for communication = 0.9, *p* for collaboration = 0.78. It means that the two groups are not significantly different.

Table 1 Students' Skills of Experimental and Control Group

		Critical thinking	Creativity	Communication	Collaboration
Experimental group	Pre test	38.54	35.32	44.23	48.67
	Post test	83.15	83.02	85.68	85.82
Control group	Pre test	37.61	34.63	44.51	48.88
	Post test	78.69	78.38	79.58	81.45

The data in Table 1 also shows the posttest score of the control group is also quite good (critical thinking = 78.69, creativity = 78.38, communication = 79.58, collaboration = 81.45). "SMK X" is a good SSVS and generally students are smart young people, so it is natural that with the direct instruction model they also get a good score. However, the t test shows a significant difference between the experimental group and the control group, so it can be concluded that CPjBL is more effective than the learning model that has been used so far.

Fig. 1. Score of Critical Thinking

Figure 1 shows the score for each indicator of critical thinking, both experimental group and control group. The mean score of experimental group is 83.15, while control group is 78.69. Table 2 shows the results of t test with $p = 0.027$, so that it can be concluded that they differ significantly. Calculation of effect size found $d = 0.50$. It means that CPjBL applied to the experimental group was able to improve students' critical thinking skills better.

When examined carefully, self-regulation is the aspect of critical thinking that gets the lowest score, both experimental group (79.16) and control group (75.69). Open interviews with teachers at the school and also with students were found that students were not used to do check and recheck for what had been done. Maybe students also master the project they are working on, so they are sure of the results of the analysis of the problems they face. This result was very similar to the results of research by Snyeder and Snyder (2008) and Samani, Cholik, and Buditjahjana (2016). It may also be that the limited time to complete the project makes it impossible for students to do “check and recheck”.

Table. 2. Result of t test on Critical Thinking

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Critical Thinking	Equal variances assumed	2.023	70	.027
	Equal variances not assumed	2.023	69.825	.027

Fig. 2. Score of Creativity

Figure 2 shows the scores obtained by students in each aspect of creativity, both experimental group and control group. The mean score of experimental group is 83.02 while control group is 73.38. Table 3 shows the results of t test with $p = 0.03$ so it illustrated that they differ significantly. The effect size calculation found $d = 0.70$, so it can be concluded that CPjBL is more effective for enhancing creativity.

Of the four aspects of creativity, the originality aspect scored was the lowest, both for the experimental group (82.98) and the control group (76.38). According to the teacher in the learning phase, students are not allowed to make breakthrough that can be harmful. It is very possible that the rules make students not dare to do new things that are not in accordance with the SOP or teacher's instructions. The manual held by students also seemed to make students not dare to make a breakthrough outside the SOP. Particularly before the lesson begins, the

Table. 3. Result of t test on Creativity

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Creative Thinking	Equal variances assumed	1.831	70	.031
	Equal variances not assumed	1.831	64.615	.032

teacher emphasized the importance of work safety, which includes the need to take the SOP. This finding is in accordance with the result of study carried out by Tan, Lee, Ponnisamy, Koh and Tan (2016).

Fig. 3. Score of Communication

Figure 3 shows the scores obtained by students in each aspect of communication, both experimental group and control group. The experimental mean score of the group is 85.68, while the control group is 79.56. Table 4 shows the results of *t* test with $p = 0.03$ so that it can be concluded that they differ significantly. Calculation of effect size found $d = 0.76$, so it illustrates that the CPjBL is more effective for improving the communication skills of SSVS students.

The communication aspect that got the lowest score was grammar, both experimental group = 84.02 and control group = 76.63. Observations during the learning process revealed that communication among SSVS students tended to use local language with slang and jargon, neglecting the formal language they should use in class. The use of such language also occurred when they had to make a report for their activities. It is very likely that the use of such languages is influenced by local customs.

Fig. 4. Score of Collaboration

Figure 4 shows the scores obtained by students in each aspect of students' ability to collaborate, both experimental group and control group. The mean score of the experimental group is 85.82 while the control group is 81.45. Table 5 shows the results of *t* test with $p = 0.08$ so that it can be concluded that they differ significantly. The calculation of effect size found $d = 0.70$, so it can be concluded that the CPjBL is more effective to improve the collaboration skills of SSVS students.

Table 4. Result of *t* test on Communication

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Communication Skill	Equal variances assumed	2.215	70	.030
	Equal variances not assumed	2.215	58.463	.031

Table 5. Result of *t* test on Collaboration

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Collaboration Skill	Equal variances assumed	3.481	70	.008
	Equal variances not assumed	3.481	57.230	.009

Among the five aspects of collaboration, aspects of responsibility and accountability are the weakest. Experimental group got a score of 85.33 while the control group received a score of 78.81. This result is similar to the study of vocation teacher candidates at the State University of Surabaya (Samani, Suparji, Rahmadian, 2017). How the students used the tools and material was observed and it resulted that their responsibility and accountability were not good. They were neither economical in using materials nor disciplined in using and storing equipment after they are used.

5 Conclusion

Based on the finding described, it can be concluded that CPjBL is effective in developing SSVS students' skills in critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration. However, this research has limitations. Firstly, the number of sample was very limited, 36 students for experimental group and 36 students for control group. Secondly, sample mostly are smart young people. Further research is needed with a larger sample originating from schools with diverse student abilities to prove whether the CPJBL is effective in increasing these four skills.

In further research, it is necessary to improve learning materials in order to improve students' abilities in the aspects of self-regulation in critical thinking, originality aspects in creativity, grammar aspects in communication and responsibility and accountability aspects in collaboration skills.

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